

Supervisory Relationship, Organizational Climate and Satisfaction of Employees in a Local Community College

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Abstract: *This study aimed to analyze the supervisory relationship, organizational climate and satisfaction of employees in a local community college. The researcher used a descriptive-correlational design with the survey as the instrument and considered 60 respondents using a convenience sampling technique. An adopted and modified instrument was used to gather data. For the statistical treatment, the study used SPSS 22 to analyze the gathered data with the use of the following tools: frequency, percentage, weighted mean, t-test, ANOVA and Pearson-r. The study generated the following results: the respondents answered, “Agree” that they have a good and suitable supervisory relationship, organizational climate and overall satisfaction. In addition, there are significant findings observed in supervisory relationships and organizational climate when grouped according to demographic profiles. Furthermore, relationship exist between some of the demographic profiles of the respondents, supervisory relationship, organizational climate and overall satisfaction. With the forgoing results, the researcher recommended important suggestions for this study.*

Keywords— leadership organizational climate, satisfaction, employees, local community college

1. INTRODUCTION

The attitude of an individual towards work is an essential component of a healthy organization. It can affect the organizational output since it is a unique trait of an individual to behave towards a certain job and even if the organization has set parameters and routines, the output is never the same to some extent. Judge, Weiss, Muller, & Hulin (2017) stated that in recent years, development in theory and method have reinvigorated research which now addresses a rich panoply of topics related to the daily flow of affect, the complexity of personal motives and dispositions, and the complex interplay of attitude objects and motivation in shaping behavior. Doing attitudinal study, help validate such important facets of organizational management.

Literatures provide different perspectives and analysis towards an employee’s attitude towards work, its team or group, to his/ her manager or supervisor. Like what Yousef in 2017 found out, that employees in the investigated departments are remaining with their current departments because they want to do so, or because they have to do so, but not because they feel they ought to do so. When it comes to gender, Selvarajan, Slattery & Stringer (2015) found that female employees have more positive work-related attitudes towards client organization than the male counterpart does. However, Zientara, Kujawski & Godfrey (2015) stated in their study that job satisfaction is not a predictor of commitment and work commitment is linked to work engagement. This only shows that it probably depends on the individuality and uniqueness of the employee which is hard to change to some extent.

Another important perspective considering this attitudinal literature is the relationships of it with other pertinent variables in the organization. For example, Selvarajan, Slattery, & Stringer (2015) showed that education and to a limited extent, age, acted as a moderator for the relationship between gender and employee attitudes. Asrar-ul-Haq, & Kuchinke (2016) revealed that there is a significant relationship between transformational leadership and employee performance outcomes in terms of effectiveness, and employee satisfaction. On the same idea, Van den Heuvel, Schalk, & van Assen, (2015) showed the relationship between trust and all three attitude toward change dimensions was mediated by psychological contract fulfillment and perceived need for change. Miao, Humphrey, & Qian (2017) showed that emotional intelligence is related to job satisfaction and relates to organizational commitment and turnover intentions. The ever-changing world of management causes drastic and dramatic turn of events in an organization’s domain and employees adapt in different ways that they can to compensate with the pace. To support this idea, Erdogan, Bauer & Taylor (2015) showed that perceived organizational support moderated the effects of management commitment to the environment on organizational justice, organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behaviors targeting the environment.

In terms of effects and benefits, studies like that of Quratulain & Khan (2015) found that public service motivation exacerbates the adverse effects of red tape on negative employee attitudes and behaviors and that these effects are transmitted through the mechanism of resigned satisfaction. In addition, Dusseau, Hammer, Crain, &

Bodner, (2016) showed in their study that significant and beneficial indirect effects of family-supportive supervisor behaviors training on chances in employee job performance, organizational commitment, engagement, job satisfaction, and turnover intentions through changes in employee perceptions of their supervisor’s overall family-supportive supervisor behaviors. Furthermore, Asio (2019) disclosed that their respondents have moderate ideas regarding bullying in the workplace. This can hamper the performance of an individual in the workplace and such thing can happen anytime and anywhere.

Other variables that plays a contributory part of attitudinal studies includes that perspectives of Bullock, Stritch & Rainey (2015) wherein they exposed that public employees expressed higher levels of public-service-oriented motives and more likely to say they receive in the form of perceived social impact. Van den Heuvel, Schalk, & van Assen, (2015) confirmed that psychological contract fulfillment, trust, and perceived need for change mediated the relationship between change information and attitude toward change. In addition, Bullock, Stritch & Rainey (2015) also mentioned that public employees placed less importance on high income as a reward and expressed higher levels of organizational commitment.

The study would like to put a premium on the attitudes of faculty and administrative personnel of a local college in Central Luzon with a primary purpose of analyzing the level of and perception of the respondents in the workplace. This baseline information will provide the administration with substantial ideas and concepts of how the individuals in the organization play within and outside of the institution.

Hopefully, this study hopes to provide the “big picture” of the institution’s workhorses and try to engage in the developing the behavioral perspective of a work environment of those individuals or groups that comes out to be a little in the defective side of organizational commitment. Last, to add to the ever-growing literature of organizational management for future researches.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

This study made use of descriptive-correlational design of research with survey as its primary instrument. According to Leavy (2014) survey research is the most used quantitative design in the social sciences, which relies on asking people standardized questions that can be analyzed. Since this study will dwell on collecting data through a survey questionnaire, it is just and fitting to use this design for this study.

2.2 Participants

Sixty (60) respondents of a local community college in Region 3 who are employed as full time in the academic

year of 2019-2020 joined the survey. A convenience sampling technique was used since the personnel’s availability and willingness to take part is anticipated.

2.3 Instrument of the Study

This study adapted and modified the International Public Management Association for Human Resources (IPMA-HR) Employee Attitude Surveys (2008). The survey comprised four major parts: the demographic profile of the respondents; supervisory relationship; organizational climate and the overall satisfaction of the respondents. The instrument underwent a reliability test and subjected it to the alpha Cronbach test.

2.4 Statistical Treatment

All the gathered data was subjected into statistical treatment using the following statistical tools: frequency and percentage for the demographic profile, weighted mean for the supervisory relationship, organizational climate and overall satisfaction of respondents, T-test and ANOVA for the significant differences of respondents’ responses and Pearson-r for relationship among the variables involved in the study. The researcher used SPSS 22 to treat the data.

3. RESULTS

This study aimed to analyze the supervisory relationship, organizational climate and overall satisfaction of employees in a local community college in Region 3, Philippines. The researcher used different statistical tool to treat the gathered data. The following presentations result from the statistical treatment of the data.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percentage
Department		
Faculty	32	53
Administration	28	47
Total	60	100
Age		
20-30 years old	23	38
31-40 years old	14	24
41-50 years old	12	20
51 years old above	11	18
Total	60	100
Sex		
Male	33	55
Female	27	45
Total	60	100
Civil Status		
Single	32	53
Married	26	43
Others	2	3
Total	60	100
Educational		

Attainment		
High School Level	5	8
High School Graduate	3	5
Vocational Course	4	7
College Level	3	5
College Graduate	21	35
Post Graduate Level	18	30
Post Graduate	6	10
Total	60	100
Employment Status		
Regular	16	27
Casual	2	3
Contract of Service	40	67
Job Order	2	3
Total	60	100
Salary		
Less than Php 5,000	4	7
Php 5,001-10,000	9	15
Php 10,001-20,000	35	58
Php 20,001-30,000	12	20
Total	60	100

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. We can deduce that the faculty department got more respondents (with 32) than the administrative department (with 28). The table also showed that 20-30 years old dominated the whole group with 23 with the male (33) dominating the female counterpart (27). In terms of civil status, there are more singles (32) than the combined numbers of married and others (28). College graduates (23) topped the list in terms of educational attainment followed by postgraduate level (21). There are more contract of service respondents (40) than regulars (16), casuals (2) and job order (2). The salary of most of the respondents is between 10,001-20,000 pesos per month. The table above provides a glimpse of the actual personnel in a local community college in Region 3, which are connected and employed to such an extent.

Table 2. Employees' Supervisory Relationship

SUPERVISORY RELATIONSHIPS	Mean	Interpretation
My supervisor fosters an atmosphere of mutual trust, respect and confidence.	4.47	Agree
My supervisor does a good job of sharing necessary information.	4.40	Agree
My supervisor clearly communicates his or her	4.32	Agree

performance expectations to me.		
I receive routine feedback from my supervisor about my job performance.	4.22	Agree
Discussions with my supervisor about my performance are beneficial	4.28	Agree
Average Mean	4.34	Agree

*Legend: 1.00-1.45 = Don't know; 1.46-2.45 = Strongly Disagree; 2.46-3.45 = Disagree; 3.46-4.45 = Agree; 4.50 – 5.00 = Strongly Agree

Table 2 represents the workplace attitudes of faculty and administrative personnel in terms of supervisory relationship. The highest mean produced is from item 1, which has 4.47 with a Likert scale equivalent of *agree*. However, it is item 4 that got the lowest mean with 4.22 which has a Likert scale equivalent of *agree*. The average mean for supervisory relationship is 4.34, which has a Likert equivalent of *agree*. This means that the respondents have a good working attitude towards their immediate supervisor in their workplace.

Table 3. Employees' Organizational Climate

ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE	Mean	Interpretation
I believe that discipline is administered fairly and consistently to all employees in my office/department.	4.17	Agree
Discipline in my office/department is administered according to Civil Service Rules.	4.17	Agree
As an employee, I feel secure in speaking up about office/department practices and/or policies that are ethically questionable.	3.93	Agree
My co-workers know the difference between ethical and unethical behaviors, and seem to care about the difference.	4.12	Agree
My office/department is serious about maintaining a work environment that is free of violence and harassment	4.40	Agree
My office/department is serious about maintaining a work environment that is free of drugs and alcohol.	4.45	Agree
My office/department creates and maintains a safe and healthy work environment by taking action which prevents injury or harm to self, others, equipment and/or property.	4.47	Agree

Average Mean	4.24	Agree
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**Legend: 1.00-1.45 = Don't know; 1.46-2.45 = Strongly Disagree; 2.46-3.45 = Disagree; 3.46-4.45 = Agree; 4.50 – 5.00 = Strongly Agree*

Table 3 represents the workplace attitudes of faculty and administrative personnel in terms of organizational climate. The item with the highest mean score is item 7 with 4.47 with an equivalent Likert scale of *agree*. However, it is item 3 that got the lowest mean with 3.92 which is equivalent to *agree* in the Likert scale. The overall average mean for organizational climate is 4.24, which is equivalent to *agree* in the Likert scale. The results of the survey mean they have a balanced atmosphere of working relationship within the organization.

Table 4. Employees' Overall Satisfaction

OVERALL SATISFACTION,	Mean	Interpretation
Overall, I am satisfied with my job.	4.25	Agree
Overall, I feel positive about working for the office/department.	4.28	Agree
Overall, I feel that I am as productive as I can be.	4.33	Agree
Overall, I am motivated to do good work.	4.43	Agree
Overall, I am committed to achieving the goals of the office/department.	4.48	Agree
Average Mean	4.36	Agree

**Legend: 1.00-1.45 = Don't know; 1.46-2.45 = Strongly Disagree; 2.46-3.45 = Disagree; 3.46-4.45 = Agree; 4.50 – 5.00 = Strongly Agree*

Table 4 presents the workplace attitudes of faculty and administrative personnel in terms of overall satisfaction, morale, productivity, motivation and commitment. Item 5 got the highest mean score of 4.48, which is agree in the Likert scale. Item 1 got the lowest mean score of 4.25, which has a corresponding interpretation of agree in the scale. Overall, the average mean is 4.36, which is interpreted as agree on the Likert scale. This can only mean that overall; the employees' satisfaction is good as reflected with their own perspective of working in the organization.

Table 5. T-test for Significant Differences in the Supervisory Relationship, Organizational Climate and Overall Satisfaction of Respondents when grouped according to Department

	Faculty (32)		Admin (28)		t- test
	M	SD	M	SD	
	Supervisory Relationship	4.49	0.43	4.18	
Organizational Climate	4.25	0.42	4.26	0.59	-0.04 (.965)
Overall	4.36	0.46	4.38	0.48	-0.13 (.895)

Satisfaction	
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*df = 58 *p = > .05*

Table 5 shows the t-test for the significant difference in the supervisory relationship, organizational climate and overall satisfaction of respondents when grouped according to department. We can deduct that there is no significant difference in the supervisory relationship [$t(58) = 1.86, p = .068$], organizational climate [$t(58) = -0.04, p = .965$] and overall satisfaction [$t(58) = -0.13, p = .895$]. The t values of the three variables are higher than the alpha significance level of .05. This means that regardless of the department the supervisory relationship, organizational climate and overall satisfaction do not vary that much.

Table 6. T-test for Significant Differences on the Supervisory Relationship, Organizational Climate and Overall Satisfaction of Respondents when grouped according to Sex

	Male (33)		Female (27)		t- test
	M	SD	M	SD	
	Supervisory Relationship	4.32	0.74	4.37	
Organizational Climate	4.33	0.43	4.17	0.57	1.23 (.224)
Overall Satisfaction	4.44	0.48	4.29	0.44	1.23 (.224)

*df = 58 *p = > .05*

Table 6 show the t-test for the significant difference in the supervisory relationship, organizational climate and overall satisfaction of respondents when grouped according to sex. As seen in the table there is no significant difference in the supervisory relationship [$t(58) = -0.28, p = .775$], organizational climate [$t(58) = 1.23, p = .224$] and overall satisfaction [$t(58) = 1.23, p = .224$] of the respondents when grouped according to sex. The t values are higher than the alpha significance level of .05. This only means that sex is not an issue in dealing with supervisory relationship, organizational climate and overall satisfaction of the respondents.

Table 7. ANOVA for Significant Differences on Employees' Supervisory Relationship when grouped according to Demographic Profiles

		SS	dF	MS	F value
Age	Between Groups	3.735	3	1.245	3.23 (.029)*
	Within Total	21.632	56	0.386	
		25.367	59		
Highest Educational Attainment	Between Groups	8.898	6	1.483	4.77 (.001)*
	Within Total	16.469	53	0.311	
		25.367	59		
Salary	Between	4.104	4	1.026	2.65

Groups				(.043)*
Within	21.264	55	0.387	
Total	25.367	59		

*p < .05

Table 7 shows the analysis for significant differences between employees' supervisory relationship when grouped according to demographic profiles. As observed, there are a significant difference in the age, $F(3, 56) = 3.23, p = .029$; highest educational attainment, $F(6, 53) = 4.77, p = .001$; and salary, $F(4, 55) = 2.65, p = .043$. The F values are lower than the alpha significance level of .05. This only means that the supervisory relationship varies depending on the age, educational attainment and salary of the respondents.

Table 8. ANOVA for Significant Differences on Employees' Organizational Climate when grouped according to Demographic Profiles

		SS	dF	MS	F value
Civil Status	Between Groups	2.092	2	1.046	4.66
	Within	12.798	57	0.225	
	Total	14.890	59		(.013)*
Highest Educational Attainment	Between Groups	3.182	6	0.530	2.40
	Within	11.708	53	0.221	
	Total	14.890	59		(.040)*
Employment Status	Between Groups	2.032	3	0.677	2.95
	Within	12.858	56	0.230	
	Total	14.890	59		(.040)*
Salary	Between Groups	3.108	4	0.415	3.63
	Within	11.782	55	0.201	
	Total	14.890	59		(.011)*

*p < .05

Table 8 displays the analysis for significant differences between employees' organizational climate when grouped according to demographic profiles. As realized, there is a significant difference in the civil status, $F(2, 57) = 4.66, p = .013$; highest educational attainment, $F(6, 53) = 2.40, p = .040$; employment status, $F(3, 56) = 2.95, p = .040$; and salary, $F(4, 55) = 3.63, p = .011$. Their F values are lower than the alpha significance of .05 levels. This means that the organizational climate differs in terms of civil status, highest educational attainment, employment status and salary of the respondents.

Table 9. Correlation Matrix between Demographic Profile, Supervisory Relationship, Organizational Climate and Overall Satisfaction of Respondents

	Supervisory Relationship	Organizational Climate	Overall Satisfaction
Department	-.237 (.068)	.006 (.965)	

Age	-.348** (.006)	-.113 (.390)	
Sex	.038 (.775)	-.159 (.224)	
Civil Status	-.251 (.054)	-.263* (.042)	
Highest Educ. Attainment	.333** (.009)	.276* (.033)	
Employment Status	-.034 (.798)	-.173 (.186)	
Salary	.257* (.047)	.166 (.206)	
Supervisory Relationship			.375** (.003)
Organizational Climate			.445** (.000)

** p < .01

* p < .05

Table 9 displays the correlation matrix between the demographic profiles, supervisory relationship, organizational climate and overall satisfaction of respondents. In terms of supervisory relationship, age, highest educational attainment, and salary we observe a low relationship since the following we get the following r values of -.348, .333 and .257 respectively. Organizational climate also yielded a low relationship with civil status ($r = -.263$) and highest educational attainment ($r = .276$). In addition, the supervisory relationship ($r = .375$) and organizational climate ($r = .445$) correlates positively with the overall satisfaction of the respondents. This means that the demographic profile correlates positively and negatively with supervisory relationship and organizational climate. Both supervisory relationship and organizational climate positively correlates with the overall satisfaction of the respondents.

4. DISCUSSION

Attitude in the workplace is an essential aspect to keep the organization working with proper administrative and management schemes. This study analyzes the supervisory relationship, organizational climate, and satisfaction of employees in a local community college in Region 3, Philippines. They can utilize the results of this study by the human resource office.

For the organization to work, supervisors are intended to manifest in the area for concerns. Supervisory relationships among the faculty and administrative personnel also got a good mean score. This signifies that supervisors are there for the workers and are willing to help them in any way they can. For Yoo and Arnold (2016), they highlighted the importance of understanding the negative influence of a stressful work environment, even on employees who have a positive attitude toward helping customers. In addition, Gatling, Kim and Milliman (2016) proposed that a supervisor's organizational commitment mediates the

negative relationship of workplace spirituality to an intention to quit. Giauque (2015) also reiterated that social support and perceived organizational support are related to positive attitudes toward change.

Organizational climate is also promoted in the institution, thus, the respondents provide a substantial score in this area. This is so since values and work ethics are promulgated within the workplace. In relation, Giauque (2015) stated that stress perception can have a negative impact on positive attitudes towards change. It is also reiterated by Lee, Park and Koo (2015) that organizational identification has a direct effect of general behavior above and beyond the effect of general attitudes. In the account of Asio, Riego de Dios and Lapuz (2019), they relate professional skills to work ethics. In addition, Kunyk, Broadwith, Morris, Diaz, Reisdorfer and Wang (2016) confirmed the critical role of psychological health and safety which plays across workplaces and organizations.

If an organization gives a premium to its constituents, these individuals will also reciprocate back to the organization. A mutual relationship is then created between the organization and the individual. Zivnuska, Kacmar, Ferguson and Carlson (2016) argued that mindfulness at work exerted a direct and indirect effect on turnover intentions and affective commitment of workers.

Statistical treatments of the data provided some interesting results. There are significant results in the supervisory relationship and organizational climate in terms of age, civil status, educational attainment, employment status, and salary. This could only mean that there are major factors that play a role in the organization and it affects each individual in their attitudes. In the study of Asio and Riego de Dios (2019), they found that there are significant differences in professional qualities, learning and innovation skills, and life and career skills of their respondents. However, for Mathieu and Babiak (2015), corporate psychopathy had the most significant influence on employee attitude. Zivnuska, Kacmar, Ferguson and Carlson (2016) suggested that mindfulness at work is an important antecedent to organizational attitudes.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, the respondents provided a consistent perspective for supervisory relationship, organizational climate and overall satisfaction. The respondents gave a uniform response of *agree* in all the three (3) variables of the study.

There are significant differences in the supervisory relationship and organizational climate of the respondents when they are grouped according to age, civil status, educational attainment, employment status, and salary. In addition, we also observed a significant relationship between certain demographic profile, supervisory relationship and organizational climate. Overall satisfaction is also related to the supervisory relationship and organizational climate of the respondents.

6. CONCLUSION

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7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusion, it is therefore recommended:

- 1) A revisit on the organization's vision, mission and goals to assess the level of commitment of the employees.
- 2) A quarterly assembly for both the faculty and administrative staff to keep update with the on-going developments within the organization.
- 3) Supervisors should also be strengthened and empowered so that front-line employees will benefit further by retooling them through leadership and management seminars and trainings.
- 4) Provide a balanced organizational atmosphere by creating transparency and fairness amongst the employees.
- 5) Provide up-to-date and timely professional development seminars, trainings, or workshops for all of the employees.

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